

A comment on *Do Multimodal Large Language Models Understand Welding?*

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Abstract

This comment re-examines the released dataset and codebase for *Do Multimodal Large Language Models Understand Welding?*, which evaluates GPT-4o and LLaVA-1.6 on weld acceptability across RV/Marine, Aeronautical, and Farming contexts and proposes WeldPrompt. The audit identifies two threats to validity. First, the construct is unstable: about a quarter of Aeronautical rejections are driven by an undisclosed process-classification rule rather than visible-defect evidence, and Farming labels frequently invoke imagined end-use rather than a different inspection threshold. Second, the image pipeline caps inputs at 512×512 and JPEG-recompresses them before inference. The reported gaps between models, datasets, and contexts are therefore consistent with these confounds before any claim about MLLM welding capability needs to be invoked.

Keywords: welding, multimodal large language models, measurement validity, reproducibility, image classification

1. Introduction

The application of multimodal large language models to weld inspection is an important and timely research direction. Reliable automated support for weld assessment could have practical value across manufacturing, training, quality assurance, and safety-critical inspection workflows, and the original

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study’s contribution [1] - a labelled multi-context dataset and an evaluation of two state-of-the-art MLLMs on it - is therefore worth taking seriously.

When the released dataset and codebase are examined together, however, the study’s measurement target is under-specified in its labels and degraded in its image-preprocessing pipeline. The labels against which the models are scored are not consistently operationalised, and the apparatus used to perform the measurement applies undisclosed transformations to the visual evidence supplied to the models.

All counts in this comment are computed over the 153-weld subset that the paper actually evaluates (95 `private` + 58 `web`, after the documented removal of 26 annotated images). The counts in Table 1 of the paper are exactly reproduced from these records, confirming the analysis below operates on the same labels as the paper’s reported metrics.

2. Construct Validity

The central premise of the paper is that MLLM performance is being evaluated on weld acceptability across three domains. Real-world visual inspection is governed by decades of standardisation - such as ISO 5817:2023 [2] for quality levels of imperfections, or sector-specific codes like AWS D17.1 for aerospace [3]. These standards operationally define acceptance via precise, measurable thresholds for specific defect classes (e.g., maximum allowable pore diameter or undercut depth). Rather than mapping to such established literature, the evaluation relies on ad-hoc contexts. While such simplifications are often intended to establish an exploratory baseline or proof-of-concept [4], an audit of the expert annotations indicates that these ad-hoc contexts fail to establish a stable visual-inspection task at all, resulting in an illusory baseline [5] that obscures the true gap to industrial readiness.

2.1. The “RV & Marine” context combines distinct safety thresholds

Combining “RV & Marine” can obscure the different risk profiles of the two environments. For example, minor surface porosity may be tolerated as a benign anomaly in some RV manufacturing settings. In marine frameworks, however, similar pinholes can become capillary pathways for saltwater ingress and rapid crevice corrosion. A combined “RV/Marine” prompt therefore gives the model no single inspection threshold to apply.

2.2. Label permutations are inconsistent with the stated strictness hierarchy

The paper frames Aeronautical as the most stringent context and Farming as the least. If the contexts shared a single conformance scale, welds accepted under stricter contexts would remain acceptable under Farming. The released labels do not exhibit that structure.

Table 1: Cross-tabulation of the three binary labels on the 153-image production set.

	RV = False		RV = True	
	Farming=F	Farming=T	Farming=F	Farming=T
Aero = False	59	16	20 [†]	30
Aero = True	0	0	7 [‡]	21

[†] RV accepted but Farming rejected, with Aeronautical also rejected.

[‡] RV and Aeronautical both accepted but Farming rejected.

27 welds are rejected for Farming despite being accepted for RV/Marine. Seven of them are also accepted for the supposedly stricter Aeronautical context. **All 27 of these inversions have an empty NarrativeFarming field** - the Farming-strictest decisions are precisely the ones for which no expert explanation is recorded. More broadly, the Farming rationale is empty for 30.7% (47/153) of the dataset, against 0.7% (1/153) for RV/Marine.

In the opposite direction, several welds rejected in RV/Marine become acceptable in Farming through an imagined end-use rather than a relaxation of inspection thresholds. A weld whose RV/Marine narrative cites “*excessive weld filler ... inadequate penetration ... lack of fusion ... excessive spatter ... possible porosity ... some undercut*” is accepted for Farming with the rationale “*Could be accepted for some applications if it was not equipment. Could be part of structure parts of barn or fence.*” (46e3a4f5-...). Another weld is passed for Farming while the narrative simultaneously notes “*Wouldn’t use on a tractor, but ok for fences and gates*” (25a52fa9-...). Farming is not a stricter or looser version of the same inspection - it substitutes an imagined-end-use projection for a standardized defect threshold.

Relatedly, the dataset collapses tentative assessments into definitive Boolean labels. In the 153-image evaluation subset, 32.5% (149/459) of the context-specific narratives contain hedging language such as “*looks like*”, “*could be*”, or “*probably*”; “*looks like*” alone appears in 27.5% (126/459). One Farming label marked acceptable states: “*It would be selective on what the job was -*

could be on certain parts, but definitely not on others. Could be acceptable for something like an old fence or putting hinges on a gate” (4e8c3a5d-...). Such language shows that some labels encode conditional, use-dependent judgments rather than the clear, context-stable ground truth implied by a Boolean scale.

2.3. Process-classification rules are layered onto visual classification

A substantial share of Aeronautical rejections are not justified by any visible weld feature - they are decisions based on the welding *process* the weld represents.

- **32% (40/125) of Aeronautical rejections** mention MIG or GMAW in the corresponding narrative.
- **25% (31/125) of Aeronautical rejections** have narratives shorter than 100 characters in which the MIG/GMAW classification is essentially the entire justification, including 12 narratives consisting literally of just “MIG”. Examples: ff48dd3f-... → “gmaw - not acceptable for aeronautical”; 3608dcee-... → “mig - not relevant for aeronautical”; 80fe2d26-... → “mig weld, so aeronautical wouldn’t take it”.

The process annotations also contain apparent inconsistencies: for example, 1357029f-... is described as a TIG weld despite visually resembling MIG/GMAW.

Identifying a welding process from a still photograph is itself a non-trivial visual-classification task on a finished bead. Disallowing that process in an aviation context is a regulatory rule, not a visual-acceptance rule. Neither piece of information is supplied in the prompt. The Aeronautical evaluation therefore conflates three sub-tasks under a single label: detect visible defects, infer the welding process from appearance, and apply unstated regulations conditional on that process. A model can be penalised on the third sub-task without making any visual error at all - and roughly a quarter of Aeronautical rejections are driven by exactly this.

3. Measurement Apparatus

The paper describes a careful selection of “*high-quality photographs of actual welds.*” The released code resizes and recompresses those photographs before any model is queried:

Listing 1: Image-loading code in scripts/read_data.py

```
MAX_PIC_SIZE = (512, 512)

def load_image_pil(guid: str) -> Image:
    guid = guid.lower()
    for ext in [".jpg", ".webp", ".png"]:
        path = f"{PICS_PATH}{guid}{ext}"
        if os.path.isfile(path):
            with Image.open(path) as im:
                # resize to at most 512x512, otherwise might get
                expensive
                im.thumbnail(MAX_PIC_SIZE)
                im = im.convert("RGB")
            return im
```

The result is then JPEG-encoded at the PIL default quality of 75. On the released set: median original maximum dimension 800 px; 118 / 153 images exceed 512 px on the longest side; the remaining **35 images are not downsampled at all**, so the pipeline is not even uniform across the dataset. Per-image pixel-count reduction is mean 54%, median 59%; **encoded image bytes drop approximately 99.3% on average** (mean 3,684 KB → 25 KB), driven jointly by downsampling and Q=75 re-encoding - including for inputs stored as PNG in the released set. Many weld-relevant cues (micro-porosity, hairline cracking, fine undercutting, surface contamination, fisheyes, mill scale) become sub-pixel patterns or compression artefacts after this transformation.

4. Conclusion

The research question this paper addresses is substantively important, but the released materials do not support the strength of the conclusions presented. On the labelling side, the three ad-hoc “contexts” ignore established welding standardisation and fail to form a single conformance scale: roughly a quarter of Aeronautical rejections are driven by an unstated process-classification rule, and the strictness hierarchy is violated in both directions due to mixed decision rules. On the implementation side, all weld images are JPEG-recompressed and most are downsampled before inference - neither of which is disclosed in §3.2. The “real-world vs. online gap,” the LLaVA underperformance, and the WeldPrompt mixed results are

each consistent with these confounds before any claim about MLLM welding capability needs to be invoked.

A constructive path forward would publish a per-context labelling codebook with explicit rules and inter-rater agreement, and run both models on original-resolution images using each provider’s documented best-quality vision pathway.

Data Availability

The data and codebase re-examined in this commentary were provided by the authors of the original article. For this audit, we used the exact version available in their public GitHub repository at commit hash 382c6e973ba0c587a32a2c54bdd40ee92b12ae70.

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